

MICROSTRUCTURE, MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND OXIDATION RESISTANCE OF C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

To overcome the poor oxidation resistance of C/C composites, anti-oxidation SiC and ZrB₂-SiC ceramics were introduced into C/C composites by chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) and precursor infiltration-pyrolysis (PIP). The microstructure, mechanical properties and oxidation resistance of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites were investigated. The ZrB₂-SiC ceramic exhibits uniform dispersion and distribution in C/C composite. The C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites pyrolyzed at 1500°C has the highest flexural strength (315 MPa) and fracture toughness (10.87 MPam^{1/2}). The flexural strength, tensile strength and compressive strength increased with temperature. The C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites exhibited low ablation characteristics in plasma ablation experiments, and the linear ablation rate was 3.67×10⁻³ mm/s. The composite material, which exhibited synergistic effect between toughening and oxidation resistance, has potential application in the field of hypersonic vehicle.

1 INTRODUCTION

The low density, high strength-weight ratio and thermal shock resistance, well strength retention under high temperature have made carbon/carbon (C/C) composites as promising candidate materials for use in rocket nozzles, hypersonic aircrafts and reentry vehicles. [1-2] However, C/C composites exhibit poor oxidation resistance in oxidizing environment at temperatures as low as 500 °C. Ceramic modification is an efficient technique to improve the oxidation resistance of C/C composites. [3] Berbon et al. [4] introduced SiC into C/C composites by CVI, which improved the oxidation resistance of the composites. Reactive melt infiltration method was adopted to reduce the preparation period and cost. [5] However, carbon matrix was damaged seriously during the reaction process, which made the mechanical properties of composites deteriorate. The precursor infiltration pyrolysis technology is an effective method to solve matrix damage. [6] ZrB₂-SiC ceramics have excellent oxidation and ablation resistance above 2000 °C, but their inherent brittleness and poor thermal shock resistance severely limit their application as high temperature structural materials. [7] In this work, ZrB₂-SiC ceramics had been adopted to achieve synergistic effect between toughening and oxidation resistance.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Material preparation

The preparation of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composite was divided into four steps: (1) C/C composites with low relative density were prepared by chemical vapor deposition. (2) C-SiC gradient interface was prepared by chemical vapor co-deposition in C/C composites. (3) SiC was deposited by chemical vapor infiltration in C/C composites. (4) ZrB₂-SiC were introduced into C/C-SiC composite by precursor infiltration-pyrolysis (PIP) of ZrB₂-SiC composite precursor.

2.2 Measurement and characterization

Flexural strength of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composite was measured by three-point bending method. The fracture toughness was measured by single-edge notched beams. Microstructure and element analysis of composite was performed on scanning electron microscopy (FEI Helios Nanolab 600i, Netherlands).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure

The microstructure of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composite was shown in Fig. 1. Relatively densified microstructure was observed in Fig. 1a. The ceramics effectively filled the space between monofilament fibers and fiber bundles in C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composite, as shown in Fig. 1b. The ZrB₂-SiC ceramic exhibits uniform dispersion and distribution in Fig. 1c. The sizes of ZrB₂-SiC ceramic grains are 50–200 nm, which is only 1/10~1/20 of the size of ceramic particles introduced by slurry infiltration. It demonstrates each ZrB₂ particle was divided into 1000–8000 particles and uniformly distributed in SiC phase, so ZrB₂ and SiC phases can exhibit synergistic antioxidant and anti-ablative resistance. Furthermore, fiber extraction was observed in Fig. 1d, which is beneficial to improve the mechanical properties of the composite.

3.2 Mechanical property

Six temperatures of 1350, 1400, 1450, 1500, 1550 and 1600 °C were selected in pyrolysis of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites. Fig. 2 shows the effect of pyrolysis temperatures on flexural strength and fracture toughness of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites. The mechanical property first increase and then decrease with the increasing of pyrolysis temperatures. As pyrolysis temperature increases, the organic-inorganic transformed more completely and the C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites have higher relative densities and mechanical properties. The C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites pyrolyzed at 1500 °C has the highest flexural strength and fracture toughness. The highest flexural strength and fracture toughness are 315 MPa and 10.87 MPam^{1/2}, respectively. With the continue increasing of pyrolysis temperature, the organic-inorganic transformation will not continue to carry forward and the grain will coarsen seriously. In addition, the severe fiber damage occurred at higher temperature which is detrimental to the mechanical properties of composites.

The variation of flexural strength, tensile strength and compressive strength of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ with temperature were studied. The evolution of mechanical properties of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites at high temperature was further analyzed.

The combination of carbon fibers with carbon, silicon carbide and zirconium boride in C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composite overcomes the intrinsic brittleness of ZrB₂-SiC ultra-high temperature ceramics. The C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites have excellent properties of both high strength and high toughness due to the toughening and external force dissipation through the mechanisms of interfacial debonding, fracture and pullout of carbon fibers. The room temperature mechanical properties of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites were tested. The flexural strength, tensile strength and compressive strength of the composites are shown in Fig. 3a. It can be seen that the flexural strength of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composite at room temperature is 307.4 MPa, the average tensile strength is 123.6 MPa, and the average compressive strength is 358.6 MPa. The flexural strength of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites is higher than the tensile strength. This is because the maximum stress occurs from the outer surface of the center of the beam during the flexural test, while the maximum stress acts on the whole section during the tensile test.

The flexural, tensile and compressive strengths of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites at 600-1700 °C were tested, respectively. The test results are shown in Fig. 3b. The flexural strength of the composites increases gently in the temperature range of 600-900 °C and 1500-1700 °C, while flexural strength of the composites increases greatly in the temperature range of 900-1200 °C. The maximum flexural strength of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composite at high temperature is 489 MPa. The tensile strength of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites increases from 125 MPa to 206 MPa as the temperature increases from 600 to 1700 °C. In addition, the tensile strength of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites increases slowly before 1500 °C, and increases greatly when the temperature rises to 1700 °C. As for compressive strength of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites, the value increases linearly with temperature. The maximum compressive strength of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites at high temperature is 432 MPa.

Generally, the strength of materials decreases with the increase of temperature, whereas the strength of carbon fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites increases with the increase of temperature. This feature enables the material to exhibit stable mechanical properties at high temperatures.

3.3 Oxidation resistance

In order to evaluate the ablation performance of coatless C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites, plasma ablation experiments were used to evaluate the ablation performance of the composites. The size of the sample was 30 × 30 × 10mm, the ablation temperature was 2000°C and the ablation time was 300 s. The macroscopic morphology of the tested samples was shown in Fig. 4. According to the ablation condition of sample surface, the sample can be divided into central ablation zone and edge ablation zone. The oxide layer on the surface of central ablation zone was thicker than that of edge ablation zone. The linear ablation rate was 3.67×10⁻³ mm/s

The microstructure and elemental analysis of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites after plasma ablation at 2000 °C for 300 s are shown in Fig. 5. The polygonal network region was observed in central ablation zone, as shown in Fig. 3a. The energy spectrum analysis of spot 1 indicates the main components are Zr, O, Si and C elements (Fig. 3b), and the content of Zr is higher than that of Si, and so the gray polygonal regions are Zr-rich regions with main component of ZrO₂. The energy spectrum analysis of spot 2 indicates the main components are Si, O, Zr and C elements (Fig. 3c), and the content of Si is higher than that of Zr, so the network between the polygonal regions is Si-rich region with main component of SiO₂. The gray ZrO₂-SiO₂ network blocks the entry of external oxygen and protects the internal material from further oxidation. The microstructure of marginal ablation region is not the same as that of central ablation zone. The gaseous B₂O₃ breaks through the surface layer and remains burst bubble (Fig. 3d). The burst bubbles have dense oxide film, as shown in Fig. 3e. The energy spectrum of the oxide film was Si and O elements. In marginal ablation region, the dense SiO₂ oxide film provides protection.

4 FIGURES AND TABLES

Fig. 1 (a-c) Microstructure and (d) fiber extraction of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites pyrolyzed at 1500°C

Fig. 2 Flexural strength and fracture toughness of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites pyrolyzed at 1350–1600°C

Fig. 3 (a) Room temperature mechanical properties room temperature and (b) High temperature mechanical properties of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites pyrolyzed at 1500 °C

Fig. 4 Macroscopic picture of C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composite (a) before and (b) after plasma ablation

Fig. 5 (a) Microstructure and (b-c) elemental analysis of central ablation area, and (d-e) microstructure and element analysis of marginal ablation region

5 CONCLUSIONS

The C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites were fabricated by chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) and precursor infiltration-pyrolysis (PIP). The mechanical property first increase and then decrease with the increasing of pyrolysis temperatures. The C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites pyrolyzed at 1500 °C has the highest flexural strength and fracture toughness. The highest flexural strength and fracture toughness are 315 MPa and 10.87 MPam^{1/2}, respectively. The flexural strength, tensile strength and compressive strength increased with temperature. The max flexural strength, tensile strength and compressive strength are 489 MPa, 206 MPa and 432 MPa, respectively. The C/C-SiC-ZrB₂ composites exhibited low ablation characteristics in plasma ablation experiments, and the linear ablation rate was 3.67×10⁻³ mm/s. The oxides of Si, Zr and B elements realize the oxidation resistance protection of composites during the ablation process.

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